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Generalised Kinematic Single-Impact and Multi-Impact Models for Rocking Structures

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ABSTRACT

The rocking motion is fundamental in earthquake engineering, as it reflects the dynamic behaviour of many structural systems. However, simulating the impacts during rocking motion remains a challenging topic, as they occur in a very short time, generate high impulsive forces, cause sudden changes in velocities and result in rapid energy losses. Several non-smooth and continuous impact models have been proposed in the literature to describe such complex phenomena, yet the notable experimental variability of the angular coefficient of restitution is not adequately interpreted. This study introduces novel single-impact and multi-impact models tailored to the dynamic peculiarities of rocking motion. The proposed single-impact model effectively captures a wide range of impact conditions of the contact interface and demonstrates notable versatility as it uniquely combines the strengths and features of available models in the rocking literature. Subsequently, the model is extended into a multi-impact model, enabling the effective simulation of consecutive impacts and possible free-flights. This enhancement increases the model's efficacy and broadens its scope of application. Importantly, the proposed models are calibrated and validated against an extensive experimental campaign of 120 free rocking tests on blocks with various aspect ratios, demonstrating enhanced predictive capabilities. Finally, a series of comparative numerical analyses reveals the influence of the proposed impact models on the dynamic response of rocking blocks.

1 | Introduction

Rocking motion resembles the dynamic behaviour of a wide range of structures [1–4], including the out-of-plane response of masonry façades [5–9]. Therefore, the accurate simulation of rocking motion is of paramount importance for many earthquake engineering applications. The dynamics of rocking motion consists of two distinct phenomena: (i) the rocking phase and (ii) the impacts. During rocking, the structure experiences a smooth rotating motion over one of its (corner) pivot points, which is rather simple to describe analytically [4, 10]. Nonetheless, the smooth rocking phase is interrupted by impacts when the block collides with its base. Contrary to the rocking phase, impacts are

complex phenomena due to their very short duration, generating high impulsive forces and causing sudden changes in the block's velocity, resulting in rapid energy losses. Therefore, efficiently describing the impacts during rocking motion remains one of the most challenging topics in rocking dynamics [11–18].

Generally, there exist three main methodological approaches for simulating impacts [19, 20]: (i) continuous models, (ii) non-smooth models, and (iii) hybrid models. Continuous models, also referred to as compliant or regularised models, describe the impact process using compliant contact force-deformation relationships and thus simulate the complete period of impact in a continuous manner [6, 21–28]. On the other hand, non-smooth

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models assume instantaneous impacts and focus on predicting the post-impact state of the system [20, 29–32]. Such models postulate sound kinematic and mechanical assumptions for the unilateral constraints, such as Signorini's impenetrability condition and the use of impulse-momentum equations provides the route to the solution [32–34]. Finally, hybrid models combine some aspects of the two preceding categories and treat the impact process as discontinuous in the time domain and continuous in the impulse domain [18, 35–38]. More specifically, each impact is assumed as an instantaneous event, within which a detailed continuous analysis is developed over a dummy time period with the aim of analysing the impulse phases of compression and restitution.

Particularly for the rocking problem, the first impact model was proposed by Housner [4]. Within the non-smooth framework, the model assumed rigid bodies and interfaces, a perfectly plastic impact at the corner contact point without sliding, hence proposing a simple formula to capture the energy loss via the angular Coefficient of Restitution (CoR). Based on the same methodological principles, a group of recent rocking impact models moved away from the assumption that the resultant of the impulsive force is strictly concentrated at the two corner points of the block and parametrised its position [11, 12, 39]. Another group of non-smooth rocking impact models challenged Housner's assumptions of perfectly plastic impacts at the contact points or the absence of sliding and suggested the use of a kinematic normal CoR that permits bouncing together with a Coulomb friction law that allows sliding [14, 29, 40, 41]. In the same non-smooth contact dynamics framework, [42–44] extended Housner's impact law by determining the post-impact mechanism through a variational formulation. A series of hybrid impact models have also been proposed for the rocking problem, which employ the energetic (Stronge's) normal CoR [35, 45], hence, ensuring consistent energy dissipation [15, 16, 18, 46–49]. Finally, continuous impact models have been extensively applied to analyse rocking motion, commonly employing unilateral springs and viscous dashpots [6, 26, 50–53], or even more advanced nonlinear viscous damping models [23, 24].

Experimental free-rocking studies play a crucial role in understanding the impact dynamics and energy losses of rocking structures. Such studies not only enable direct observation of the complex impact phenomena and quantification of the energy dissipation but also facilitate the calibration and performance evaluation of different impact models. Key challenges in experimental campaigns include specimen and setup design, data acquisition and sampling rate, and post-processing of the response signal to accurately quantify energy losses. Numerous studies have reported that, in general, the experimentally extracted angular CoR differs from the prediction of Housner's model [54–59]. Recognising the significance of the impact position, few studies took measures to control where the impact occurs using concave interfaces or steel pedestals at the edges [12, 56, 60, 61], while others attempted to measure the impact location directly [39, 59]. Additionally, other works highlighted that interface and geometrical imperfections considerably influence the response [12, 13, 41, 54, 59], recognising that detailed knowledge of all the imperfections in real structures is practically impossible, prompting the need for probabilistic approaches. Further studies explored different block and interface materials [23, 60, 62, 63],

showing their substantial impact on energy dissipation, [41] for example, observed bouncing and free-flight events. Notably, several investigations reported considerable scatter in the angular CoR estimations, even among nominally identical specimens [57, 59, 60, 62, 63]. Overall, experimental campaigns have demonstrated that energy loss during impacts involves complex phenomena at the interface, which may be challenging to capture.

The present work first builds on currently available impact models and proposes a novel single-impact model that parametrises the position of the resultant impact force, adopts a kinematic normal CoR and uses the Mohr-Coulomb friction law to account for sliding. Importantly, the single-impact model integrates effectively key elements of previous models, while providing a unified and comprehensive formulation. Secondly, this paper extends the single-impact model and proposes a novel multi-impact model, enabling the simulation of consecutive impacts and potential simultaneous detachment of multiple contact points. This extension considerably increases the model's efficacy and broadens its scope of application.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the governing equations of motion of a rigid free-standing block. The complete formulations of the proposed impact models are presented in Sections 3 and 4, which rely on impulsive dynamics and the impulse-momentum equations. Consequently, Section 5 compares the proposed models with those from the literature in capturing the energy loss at impact. Section 6 conducts a twofold calibration of the models' parameters based on an extensive experimental campaign and then compares the predictions of the two models against the experimental time-history responses. Finally, Section 7 investigates the influence that the proposed impact models have on the dynamic behaviour of rocking blocks, and Section 8 summarises the conclusions of the work.

2 | Theoretical Background of the Rigid Motion of Free-Standing Block

Consider the rectangular planar rigid block shown in Figure 1a with width $2b$, height $2h$, slenderness angle $\alpha = \arctan(b/h)$, Centre of Mass CM, diagonal distance between CM and the corner C (or C') R , mass m and moment of inertia over the CM $I_{CM} = m(b^2 + h^2)/3$, standing freely (unanchored) on a rigid ground. During an earthquake, the block may uplift and start rocking over its corners C (or C') (Figure 1b), start sliding over its base (Figure 1c), or start a mixed rocking-sliding motion.

Rocking occurs when the overturning moment due to the horizontal ground acceleration \ddot{x}_g exceeds the self-centring gravity force of the block. This condition yields the minimum ground acceleration necessary for rocking to initiate: $|\ddot{x}_g| = g \cdot \tan(\alpha)$, where g is the acceleration of gravity. After initiation, the rocking motion of the block can be described using the block's rotation from the vertical θ as Degree of Freedom (DoF) (Figure 1b), and the Equation of Motion (EoM) reads [4]:

$$\ddot{\theta} = -p^2 \left[\sin(\alpha \cdot \text{sgn}(\theta) - \theta) + \frac{\ddot{x}_g}{g} \cos(\alpha \cdot \text{sgn}(\theta) - \theta) \right] \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 1 | Planar rigid block (a) freely standing on rigid ground, experiencing (b) rocking motion, (c) sliding motion, and (d) rocking-sliding motion.

where $\text{sgn}(\cdot)$ represents the signum function and p is the frequency parameter of the block, defined as $p = \sqrt{mgR/(I_{CM} + mR^2)} = \sqrt{3g/(4R)}$.

Sliding occurs when the horizontal ground acceleration (\ddot{x}_g) exceeds the frictional resistance at the interface of the block with the ground, which is commonly described using the friction coefficient μ . This condition yields the minimum ground acceleration for sliding to initiate: $|\ddot{x}_g| = g \cdot \mu$. Consequently, the sliding motion of the block can be described using the horizontal displacement of the block x as DoF (Figure 1c), and the EoM reads [40]:

$$\ddot{x} = -\text{sgn}(\dot{x}) \cdot \mu g - \ddot{x}_g \quad (2)$$

Finally, the rocking-sliding motion can initiate if $\mu \geq \tan \alpha$ and when the horizontal ground acceleration (\ddot{x}_g) exceeds $|\ddot{x}_g| = g \cdot \frac{\mu \tan^2 \alpha + 4\mu - 3 \tan \alpha}{4 \tan^2 \alpha - 3\mu \tan \alpha + 1}$ [64]. The rocking-sliding motion can be described using two DoFs (Figure 1d): (i) the horizontal displacement x , and (ii) the rotation of the block from the vertical θ . The EoMs are omitted herein for brevity, but they can be found in [40].

The rocking (and rocking-sliding) motion(s) are interrupted by impacts when the block collides with its base, changing its pivot point from one corner to the other. Housner's impact model [4] employed the angular CoR e_θ to capture the energy loss at impact, which relates the angular velocities prior ($\dot{\theta}^-$) and after ($\dot{\theta}^+$) impact as: $\dot{\theta}^+ = e_\theta \dot{\theta}^-$. It assumes a perfectly plastic impact at the collision pivot points without sliding. Considering the conservation of angular momentum over the post-impact pivot point, e_θ becomes:

$$e_{\theta, \text{Housner}} = 1 - 1.5 \sin^2 \alpha \quad (3)$$

Housner's impact model suggests that e_θ depends solely on the slenderness α of the block, providing intuitive and an easy-to-use closed-form estimation while capturing the main dissipative feature of impacts. Nevertheless, experimental evidence has shown that e_θ often differs significantly from Housner's prediction, challenging its underlying assumptions. To this end, the following Section proposes a novel generalised kinematic impact model, which provides the same prediction as Housner's impact model as a special case.

FIGURE 2 | Instants of the rigid rocking block impacting with the rigid ground: (a) before, (b) during and (c) after impact.

3 | Single-Impact Model

3.1 | Governing Equations

Consider the rectangular rigid block shown in Figure 2 colliding with its base (Figure 2b). Prior to impact, the CM of the block has horizontal, vertical and angular velocities \dot{x}^- , \dot{y}^- and $\dot{\theta}^-$, respectively (Figure 2a), while after impact the velocities become \dot{x}^+ , \dot{y}^+ and $\dot{\theta}^+$ (Figure 2c). For generality and ease of extension to multiple impacts (presented in Section 4), the model assumes that the block has an incidence angle θ^- at the instant of impact (Figure 2b). The impact generates instantaneous impact forces at the contact interface with horizontal and vertical resultants F_{px} and F_{py} , respectively. The resultant impact forces are assumed to act at a point P_λ on the interface, which is parametrised to have an arbitrary position, located at a distance λb from the CM, measured along the principal axis of the block (Figure 2b). Note that P_λ cannot lie at the half-width of the base closer to the pre-impact pivot corner, as this would generate energy during impact, which is not physically possible [11, 39]. Therefore, it is convenient to use a piecewise definition of λ , physically admissible for $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ [11, 39]. The value of λ may be known for a given problem (e.g., due to specific bumps at the interface [12], or intentionally designed protruding edges [58]) or assumed to be variable and treated as an uncertain input parameter [11] (such as the calibration conducted in Section 6 later on), λ is equal to 1 when the incidence angle θ^- is nonzero (i.e., corner impact), while λ equals zero when the impact point is located at the midpoint of the base.

The impact problem involves determining the three unknown velocities after impact: \dot{x}^+ , \dot{y}^+ and $\dot{\theta}^+$, based on the given set of velocities before impact: \dot{x}^- , \dot{y}^- and $\dot{\theta}^-$, while the rotation of the block is assumed constant during impact, i.e., $\theta^- = \theta^+$. To solve the problem, the unknown velocities are related to the given velocities by applying the linear and angular impulse-momentum equations before and after impact [40]: Linear impulse-momentum equation over the x axis:

$$m\dot{x}^- + \int F_{Px} dt = m\dot{x}^+ \quad (4)$$

Linear impulse-momentum equation over the y axis:

$$m\dot{y}^- + \int F_{Py} dt = m\dot{y}^+ \quad (5)$$

Angular impulse-momentum equation over the CM:

$$I_{CM}\dot{\theta}^- + \left(\lambda \text{bsgn}\dot{\theta}^- \sin \theta^- + h \cos \theta^- \right) \int F_{Px} dt - \left(\lambda \text{bsgn}\dot{\theta}^- \cos \theta^- - h \sin \theta^- \right) \int F_{Py} dt = I_{CM}\dot{\theta}^+ \quad (6)$$

where $\int F_{Px} dt$ and $\int F_{Py} dt$ are the impulses introduced by the impact forces F_{Px} and F_{Py} , respectively, over the infinitesimally short impact time. The system of the three Equations (4)–(6) involves five unknowns: \dot{x}^+ , \dot{y}^+ , $\dot{\theta}^+$, $\int F_{Px} dt$ and $\int F_{Py} dt$. Therefore, two additional governing equations are needed to uniquely determine the post-impact velocities. The first additional condition is introduced by the kinematic normal CoR (or Newton's CoR) that relates the velocity normal to the interface before and after impact at the impact point P_λ :

$$\dot{y}_p^+ = -e_N \dot{y}_p^- \quad (7)$$

where \dot{y}_p^- and \dot{y}_p^+ are the vertical (normal) velocities of the block at the point P_λ before and after the impact, respectively, and $e_N \in [0, 1]$ is the kinematic normal CoR [37, 65]. The assumption that the block is rigid allows the motion of the CM to be related directly to the motion at the impact point P_λ : $\dot{y}_p = \dot{y} - (\lambda \text{bsgn}\dot{\theta} \cos \theta - h \sin \theta)\dot{\theta}$. Therefore, Equation (7) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{y}^+ - \left(\lambda \text{bsgn}\dot{\theta}^+ \cos \theta^- - h \sin \theta^- \right) \dot{\theta}^+ \\ = -e_N \left[\dot{y}^- - \left(\lambda \text{bsgn}\dot{\theta}^- \cos \theta^- - h \sin \theta^- \right) \dot{\theta}^- \right] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The second additional equation comes from the frictional behaviour of the impact interface. This study adopts the classic Mohr-Coulomb friction model with stiction, which is described by the friction coefficient μ as a function of the static and dynamic friction coefficients, μ_s and μ_d , respectively:

$$\mu(\dot{x}) = \begin{cases} \mu_s, & \text{if } \dot{x} = 0 \\ \mu_d, & \text{if } \dot{x} \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The frictional model suggests that the interface will experience sliding only if the ratio of shear to normal resultant forces (or impulses) exceeds the friction coefficient. This introduces the

following complementary sliding condition that needs to be evaluated to determine if the block will slide or not:

$$\text{Sliding will not occur} (\dot{x}_p^+ = 0) \text{ if } \mu(\dot{x}_p^-) > \left| \frac{\int F_{Px} dt}{\int F_{Py} dt} \right| \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Sliding will occur} (\dot{x}_p^+ \neq 0) \text{ if } \mu(\dot{x}_p^-) = \left| \frac{\int F_{Px} dt}{\int F_{Py} dt} \right| \quad (11)$$

At this stage, there are five unknowns: \dot{x}^+ , \dot{y}^+ , $\dot{\theta}^+$, $\int F_{Px} dt$ and $\int F_{Py} dt$, and five governing equations: Equations (4)–(6), (8), and (10) or (11), which define the impact problem. The system is solved twice in the following Sections, firstly assuming that sliding does not occur (i.e., Equations (4)–(6), (8) and (10)), and, afterwards, considering that sliding occurs (i.e., Equations (4)–(6), (8) and (11)).

3.2 | Prevention of Sliding

Assuming that there is sufficient friction to prevent sliding (i.e., Equation (10) holds) implies that the impact point P_λ will have zero horizontal velocity after impact:

$$\dot{x}_p^+ = 0 \quad (12)$$

The rigidity of the block allows the motion of the CM to be related to the motion at the impact point P_λ : $\dot{x}_p = \dot{x} + (\lambda \text{bsgn}\dot{\theta} \sin \theta + h \cos \theta)\dot{\theta}$. Hence, Equation (12) becomes:

$$\dot{x}^+ = - \left(\lambda \text{bsgn}\dot{\theta}^+ \sin \theta^- + h \cos \theta^- \right) \dot{\theta}^+ \quad (13)$$

Consequently, the problem is reformulated in dimensionless terms by setting: $S_x^- = \frac{\dot{x}^-}{h\dot{\theta}^-}$, $S_y^- = \frac{\dot{y}^-}{b\dot{\theta}^-}$, $S_x^+ = \frac{\dot{x}^+}{h\dot{\theta}^+}$, $S_y^+ = \frac{\dot{y}^+}{b\dot{\theta}^+}$ and $e_\theta = \dot{\theta}^+ / \dot{\theta}^-$, with the case of the block experiencing rocking motion before impact corresponds to $S_x^- = -1$ and $S_y^- = -\text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}^-)$. Solving Equations (4)–(6), (8) and (13) gives:

$$e_{\theta,S} = \frac{\tan^2 \alpha + 1 - 3C_1 S_x^- + 3C_2 (e_N + 1) \tan \alpha S_y^- - 3e_N C_2^2}{\tan^2 \alpha (1 + 3\lambda^2 \text{sgn} e_{\theta,S}) + 4} \quad (14)$$

$$S_y^+ = \frac{e_N}{e_{\theta,S}} \left(\frac{C_2}{\tan \alpha} - S_y^- \right) + \frac{C_3}{\tan \alpha} \quad (15)$$

$$S_x^+ = -C_4 \quad (16)$$

where the subscript ‘‘S’’ in $e_{\theta,S}$ stands for the Single-impact model, and the terms C_1 , C_2 , C_3 and C_4 are defined as:

$$C_1 = \left(\lambda \tan \alpha \text{sgn}\dot{\theta}^- \sin \theta^- + \cos \theta^- \right)$$

$$C_2 = \left(\lambda \tan \alpha \text{sgn}\dot{\theta}^- \cos \theta^- - \sin \theta^- \right)$$

$$C_3 = \left(\lambda \tan \alpha \text{sgn}\dot{\theta}^- \text{sgn} e_{\theta,S} \cos \theta^- - \sin \theta^- \right)$$

$$C_4 = \left(\lambda \tan \alpha \text{sgn}\dot{\theta}^- \text{sgn} e_{\theta,S} \sin \theta^- + \cos \theta^- \right) \quad (17)$$

Calculation of $e_{\theta,S}$ in Equation (14) requires knowledge of its sign, which is not known in advance. To address this, one can initially

assume a positive sign, calculate $e_{\theta,S}$ through Equation (14), and then evaluate the preceding assumption. If the assumption holds, then the solution for $e_{\theta,S}$ is accepted. Otherwise, a negative sign is assumed, and $e_{\theta,S}$ is re-calculated. Assuming pure rocking before impact (i.e., $\theta^- = 0$, $S_x^- = -1$ and $S_y^- = -\text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}^-)$) and $\lambda = 1$, Equation (14) leads to the pertinent equations of [29, 40, 41]. For $\theta^- = 0$, $S_x^- = -1$, $S_y^- = -\lambda \cdot \text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}^-)$ and $e_N = 0$, Equation (14) gives the pertinent equation of [39]. Moreover, Equation (14) provides energy dissipation equivalence with the model of Housner [4] (i.e., Equation (3)) for any pair of λ and e_N that satisfies the following equation:

$$e_N = \frac{\left(1 - \frac{3}{2} \sin^2 \alpha\right) \left[\tan^2 \alpha (1 + 3\lambda^2 \text{sgn} e_{\theta,S}) + 4\right] - \tan^2 \alpha - 1 + 3C_1 S_x^- - 3C_2 \tan \alpha S_y^-}{3C_2 (\tan \alpha S_y^- - C_2)} \quad (18)$$

and with the model of [11] for any pair of λ and e_N that result in zero vertical velocity at the corners of the block after impact and, hence, satisfy the following equation:

$$e_N = \frac{(\tan^2 \alpha + 1 - 3C_1 S_x^- + 3C_2 \tan \alpha S_y^-) \left[\tan \alpha \text{sgn} \dot{\theta}^- \text{sgn} e_{\theta,S} \cos \theta^- (1 - \lambda)\right]}{(C_2 - \tan \alpha S_y^-) (\tan^2 \alpha (1 + 3\lambda^2 \text{sgn} e_{\theta,S}) + 4) + (-3C_2 \tan \alpha S_y^- + C_2^2) \left[\tan \alpha \text{sgn} \dot{\theta}^- \text{sgn} e_{\theta,S} \cos \theta^- (1 - \lambda)\right]} \quad (19)$$

3.3 | Occurrence of Sliding

Assuming that there is insufficient friction to prevent sliding (i.e., Equation (11) holds) implies that the friction impact force (or impulse) will be governed by the Mohr-Coulomb friction model:

$$\int F_{Px} dt = -\text{sgn}(\dot{x}_p^+) \mu_d \int F_{Py} dt \quad (20)$$

Solving the system of Equations (4), (5), (6), (8) and (20) gives:

$$e_{\theta,S} = \frac{\tan^2 \alpha + 1 + [3(e_N + 1) \tan \alpha S_y^- - 3e_N C_2] [C_1 \mu_d \text{sgn}(C_5) + C_2]}{\tan^2 \alpha + 1 + 3C_3 [C_1 \mu_d \text{sgn}(C_5) + C_2]} \quad (21)$$

$$S_y^+ = \frac{e_N}{e_{\theta,S}} \left(\frac{C_2}{\tan \alpha} - S_y^- \right) + \frac{C_3}{\tan \alpha} \quad (22)$$

$$S_x^+ = \frac{S_x^-}{e_{\theta,S}} + \mu_d \tan \alpha \left(\frac{S_y^-}{e_{\theta,S}} - S_y^- \right) \text{sgn}(C_5) \quad (23)$$

where:

$$\text{sgn}(C_5) = \text{sgn} \left[(S_{x2} + C_4) \left(S_{y2} - \frac{S_{y1}}{e_{\theta,S}} \right) \right] \quad (24)$$

Similar to the sliding prevention case, the calculation of $e_{\theta,S}$ in Equation (21) requires knowledge of both its sign and the sign of Equation (24). To address this, it is recommended to initially assume a positive sign for $e_{\theta,S}$ and Equation (24), and then calculate Equations (21)–(23). If the initial assumptions hold, then the solution is accepted. If not, a negative sign for $e_{\theta,S}$ is tested, and the equations are re-evaluated. If this assumption is also rejected, a negative sign is assumed for Equation (24), and the process is repeated until a consistent solution is found. Assuming

rocking before impact (i.e., $\theta^- = 0$, $S_x^- = -1$ and $S_y^- = -\text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}^-)$) and $\lambda = 1$, Equation (21) leads to the pertinent equation of [40]. Additionally for $\mu_d = 0$, Equation (21) provides the pertinent equation of [29], which is also in agreement with the works of [14, 66] for $e_N = 0$.

3.4 | Sliding Condition and Physical Constraints

The sliding condition in Equations (10) and (11) can be written using the dimensionless formulation as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sliding will not occur} (\dot{x}_p^+ = 0) \text{ if } & \frac{|S_x^+ e_{\theta,S} - S_x^-|}{\tan \alpha |S_y^+ e_{\theta,S} - S_y^-|} \\ < \begin{cases} \mu_s, & \text{if } S_x^- = -C_1 \\ \mu_d, & \text{if } S_x^- \neq -C_1 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sliding will occur} (\dot{x}_p^+ \neq 0) \text{ if } & \frac{|S_x^+ e_{\theta,S} - S_x^-|}{\tan \alpha |S_y^+ e_{\theta,S} - S_y^-|} \\ = \begin{cases} \mu_s, & \text{if } S_x^- = -C_1 \\ \mu_d, & \text{if } S_x^- \neq -C_1 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

However, to evaluate $e_{\theta,S}$, S_x^+ and S_y^+ in Equations (25) and (26) it is required to know whether the block slides after impact. To address this, the following trial-and-error approach is suggested: first, assume that sliding is prevented and calculate $e_{\theta,S}$, S_x^+ and S_y^+ using Equations (14)–(16). Next, check the sliding condition using Equation (25). If the condition is satisfied, the assumption of no sliding and the corresponding solution are accepted. If not, re-calculate $e_{\theta,S}$, S_x^+ and S_y^+ using Equations (21)–(23).

Finally, the solution of the single-impact model should satisfy three additional physical constraints: (i) the total energy of the system cannot increase, meaning energy can only be lost or preserved, (ii) the vertical impulse $\int F_{Py} dt$ must be nonnegative, as tensile forces are not admissible, and (iii) the block cannot penetrate the ground, meaning that the vertical velocities of the corners of the block cannot be negative. Considering that the potential energy remains constant at impact, the first constraint implies that the kinetic energy (Z) cannot increase:

$$Z^- \geq Z^+ \Rightarrow \frac{1}{e_{\theta,S}^2} \frac{3(S_x^-)^2 + 3(S_y^-)^2 \tan^2 \alpha + \tan^2 \alpha + 1}{3(S_x^+)^2 + 3(S_y^+)^2 \tan^2 \alpha + \tan^2 \alpha + 1} \geq 1 \quad (27)$$

Enforcing the energy-loss constraint (Equation (27)) is necessary given that the kinematic normal CoR is used, which is known to

FIGURE 3 | Workflow of the single-impact model.

be energy-inconsistent when oblique impacts with friction occur, as it disregards potential frictional impulse or slip reversals. As a remedy to this problem, Stronge’s energetic normal coefficient of restitution has been proposed ([35, 45]) and adopted by hybrid impact models ([15, 16, 18, 46–49]), which enforces a global energy balance and avoids such inconsistencies. Practically, for blocks experiencing rocking motion prior to impact (i.e., $\theta^- = 0$, $S_x^- = -1$ and $S_y^- = -\text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}^-)$), the condition of Equation (27) is violated only for very stocky blocks that are beyond the interest of this study, e.g., $h/b \leq 1$ for $\lambda = 1$ and $e_N = 0.5$, or $h/b \leq \sqrt{2}$ for $\lambda = 1$ and $e_N = 1$. The second constraint implies that:

$$\int F_{py} dt \geq 0 \Rightarrow \text{sgn}(e_{\theta,s} S_y^+ - S_y^-) \text{sgn} \dot{\theta}^- \geq 0 \quad (28)$$

For blocks experiencing pure rocking motion prior to impact, the condition of Equation (28) is never violated if the condition of Equation (27) is satisfied. The third constraint implies that:

$$\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) \geq 0 \Rightarrow \text{sgn}(e_{\theta,s} \dot{\theta}^-) \text{sgn}\left(S_y^+ \pm \cos \theta^- + \frac{\sin \theta^-}{\tan \alpha}\right) \geq 0 \quad (29)$$

where the symbol “ \pm ” corresponds to “+” and “-” for the right and left corners of the block, respectively. Practically, this condition is violated for pairs of λ and e_N with low values, further discussed in Sections 4 and 5, later on.

3.5 | Summary of the Single-Impact Model

To summarise, the proposed single-impact model treats the impact event of a rigid rocking block as instantaneous, characterised by a sudden change in velocities without any change in displacements or rotations. The position of the resultant reaction forces is parametrised by the variable λ , allowing it to be positioned at any point along the interface, while the impact can occur at any arbitrary angle θ^- . The impact problem is solved using the linear and angular impulse-momentum equations, along with a kinematic normal CoR e_N and a Mohr-Coulomb friction model with stiction. Figure 3 summarises the workflow of the single-impact model.

4 | Multi-Impact Model

This Section extends the single-impact model to a multi-impact model, allowing for multiple consecutive impacts until the block transitions to a smooth rocking motion. These impacts may occur at different points along the contact interface, with the block potentially entering a free-flight phase between consecutive impacts. Specifically, the core of the multi-impact model remains the single-impact model of Section 3. The analysis proceeds by examining the motion of the block at the end of every single impact. The multi-impact model relaxes the third physical constraint of the single-impact model, and if the corners of the block exhibit a downward velocity, a consecutive impact is assumed to occur immediately. Conversely, if the corners have an upward velocity, the block is considered to enter a free-flight phase until it eventually impacts the base again, resulting in another single impact. Following this framework, Section 4.1 introduces the necessary equation to evaluate the velocities of the corners of the block, along with the equations governing the free-flight phase. Subsequently, Section 4.2 presents a summary of the multi-impact model.

4.1 | Corner Velocity and Free-Flight

At the end of each single-impact event, the subsequent motion of the block is decided based on the vertical velocities of its two corners. Let \dot{y}_C^+ denote the vertical (normal) velocity of a corner immediately after impact. If at least one corner has a downward velocity ($\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) = -1$), a consecutive impact is assumed to occur at a different point along the interface (with a larger λ). If one corner has zero vertical velocity ($\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) = 0$), the block starts pivoting about that corner and transitions to smooth rocking. Finally, if both corners have upward velocities ($\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) = +1$), the block loses contact with the base and enters a short free-flight phase.

To implement this decision rule, the sign of the post-impact corner velocities ($\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+)$) is expressed in terms of the single-impact solution, exploiting the rigidity of the block. The vertical corner velocities are obtained as:

$$\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) = \text{sgn}(e_{\theta,s} \dot{\theta}^-) \text{sgn}\left(S_y^+ \pm \cos \theta^- + \frac{\sin \theta^-}{\tan \alpha}\right) \quad (30)$$

where the symbol “ \pm ” corresponds to “+” and “-” for the right and left corners of the block, respectively. The single-impact model considers a downward corner velocity physically inadmissible in order to avoid penetration (Equation (29)). In contrast, the multi-impact model relaxes this constraint: if any corner has a downward velocity ($\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) = -1$), a new impact is assumed to occur at a different position with a larger λ . If $\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) = 0$ for one corner, the block pivots about that corner and transitions to smooth rocking. Specifically, when sliding is prevented, this corresponds to values of λ and e_N that satisfy Equation (19), i.e., the limit of the third physical constraint (Equation (29)). Finally, if both corners have upward velocity ($\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) = +1$), the block loses contact and enters a short free-flight phase [41]. The subsequent impact is again analysed with the single-impact model, but with updated initial conditions, obtained by solving the free-flight problem.

The free-flight problem uses the post-impact state of the preceding impact as initial conditions. The three equations of motion of the free-flight are:

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{x} &= 0 \\ \ddot{y} &= -g \\ \ddot{\theta} &= 0\end{aligned}\quad (31)$$

The unknown to be determined is the time the free-flight ends, which corresponds to the instant that any corner of the block contacts the base and results in a subsequent impact. The vertical position of the two corners of the block (y_C) can be determined by solving the equations of motion at the CM and relating this to the position of the corners:

$$\begin{aligned}y_C(t) &= -\frac{1}{2}gt^2 + \dot{y}^+t \pm b \left[\sin\theta^+ - \sin(\dot{\theta}^+t + \theta^+) \right] \\ &+ h \left[\cos\theta^+ - \cos(\dot{\theta}^+t + \theta^+) \right]\end{aligned}\quad (32)$$

where \dot{y}^+ , $\dot{\theta}^+$ and θ^+ (with $\theta^+ = \theta^-$) are the vertical velocity, the angular velocity and the rotation of the CM of the block after the pre-flight impact, respectively, and the symbol “ \pm ” in Equation (32) corresponds to “+” and “-” for the right and left corners of the block, respectively. Detection of the subsequent impact requires identifying the time t^{imp} at which Equation (32) first reaches zero. Therefore, the following problem is sought:

$$t^{imp} = \min \{t > 0 : y_C(t) = 0\}\quad (33)$$

After solving Equation (33), the initial conditions of the subsequent impact at the end of the free-flight can be computed as:

$$\dot{\theta}^{imp} = \dot{\theta}^+\quad (34)$$

$$S_y^{imp} = -\frac{gt^{imp}}{b\dot{\theta}^+} + S_y^+\quad (35)$$

$$S_x^{imp} = S_x^+\quad (36)$$

$$\theta^{imp} = \dot{\theta}^+t^{imp} + \theta^-\quad (37)$$

The preceding analysis demonstrates that the free-flight motion is smooth (Equation (31)) and detection of the successive impact well-posed (Equation (33)). Therefore, a general numerical integration scheme may incorporate the free-flight as a distinct type

of smooth motion that initiates after an impact, when both corners of the block exhibit an upwards velocity ($\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+) = +1$), and terminates until the next impact of the block with the base occurs (Equation (33)). Alternatively, inspired by the hybrid impact models [15, 16, 18, 46–49], this work suggests the withdrawal of the free-flight, as a distinct type of motion from the general numerical integration architecture, and proposes its incorporation into the overall workflow of the multi-impact model. This strategy is endorsed by the facts that: (i) the free-flight duration is very short in comparison with the smooth period of the rocking motion (with a relatively maximum duration typically less than 0.5%, as shown below in Section 5), and (ii) the differential equations (Equation (31)) have closed-form solutions (Equations (32)–(37)). A short dummy time step can thus be used to solve the free-flight problem and provide the initial conditions for the next impact, without resorting to a more complex scheme that frequently switches motion types and changes the number of DoFs (from 1 DoF for smooth rocking to 3 DoFs for free-flight). Finally, although the free-flight analysis does not retain the dimensionless formulation of the single-impact model, Section 5 shows numerically that the problem remains dimensionally equivalent, as blocks of different sizes yield identical solutions.

4.2 | Summary of the Multi-Impact Model

Figure 4 illustrates the overall workflow of the multi-impact model. A unified angular CoR, denoted as $e_{\theta,M}$ (where the subscript “M” stands for Multi-impact) and initialised to unity, is used to account for all consecutive impacts. Essentially, $e_{\theta,M}$ provides a joint angular CoR that simultaneously considers all the multiple impacts within the model.

The analysis begins with the first single-impact event (Section 3), using the block’s geometry, pre-impact velocities, and the assumed model parameters (λ , e_N , μ_s and μ_d). At the end of the first impact, $e_{\theta,M}$ is updated, and the velocities at the corners of the block are determined using Equation (30).

If the vertical velocity of any corner is downwards (i.e., $\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+)$ is negative), a consecutive single impact occurs, with the initial conditions being the outcomes of the previous impact. In this case, the new impact position will have a larger λ value. Consecutive chattering (also referred to as “rattling” [67, 68]) may be simulated this way, but excessive repetitions should be avoided by using a counter i with a predefined threshold i_{max} and the use of $\lambda = 1$, as the block will eventually pivot over its corner.

If the vertical velocities at the corners of the block are both upwards (i.e., $\text{sgn}(\dot{y}_C^+)$ is positive), then the block enters a free-flight phase. The free-flight is analysed using Equations (32)–(37) and the results provide the initial conditions for the next single-impact. The impact following a free-flight is assumed to occur at one of the corners of the block (i.e., the corner that contacts the base first), thus $\lambda = 1$. After the subsequent impact, $e_{\theta,M}$ is updated and the corner velocities are re-evaluated.

If the vertical velocities are upwards, another free-flight occurs [41], using the impact’s results as the initial conditions. Similarly, repeated free-flights and impacts can be simulated,

FIGURE 5 | Angular CoR $e_{\theta,S}$ of the single-impact model of Figure 3 for different block aspect ratios: (a) various λ , for $e_N = 1$ and $\mu_s = \mu_d = 0.6$; (b) various e_N , for $\lambda = 1$ and $\mu_s = \mu_d = 0.6$; (c) various μ_s and μ_d , for $\lambda = 1$ and $e_N = 0$; (d) comparison with the models of Shenton and Jones [40] and Chatzis et al. [11].

Finally, Figure 5d compares the proposed single-impact model with other impact models from the literature. More specifically, the proposed model is equivalent to the model of Shenton and Jones [40] (and subsequently [14, 29, 41, 66]) for any e_N , μ_s or μ_d by setting the impact position at the corner (i.e., $\lambda = 1$). Similarly, the proposed model can replicate the model of Chatzis et al. [11] (and subsequently [12, 39]) for any impact position λ . Note that to attain exact equivalence with [11], sliding is excluded and e_N is calculated using Equation (19) that represents a zero post-impact velocity (\dot{y}_C^+) at the corner.

Figure 6a illustrates the behaviour of the angular CoR $e_{\theta,M}$ (Figure 4) of the multi-impact model for blocks with aspect ratios $2 < h/b < 16$, assuming that the first impact occurs at an intermediate position with $\lambda_0 = 0.5$ and experience consecutive plastic impacts (i.e., $e_N = 0$) at different equally-spaced positions λ_i . Three different maximum numbers of impacts i_{max} are considered, 1, 5 and 25, showing negligible differences among them (Figure 6a). This indicates that consecutive chattering along the interface has a minimal influence on the angular CoR, and the model is not sensitive to the chosen value of i_{max} , which is hereafter assumed to be 5. Nevertheless, Figure 6a shows a noteworthy difference between the multi-impact model and the single-impact model, which considers only a single impact at the assumed position with $\lambda_0 = 0.5$, while a more comprehensive comparison of the models across various combinations of λ and e_N is presented later. Similarly, Figure 6b investigates the influence of the spacing of the consecutive impact positions λ_i (increment of λ) by randomly varying their spacing for 100 different instances, and for the same configuration as Figure 6a with $\lambda_0 = 0.5$, $e_N = 0$ and $i_{max} = 5$. Figure 6b shows negligible differences between the equally-spaced and the 100 randomly-spaced instances, demonstrating that the exact spacing distribution of the λ_i of the consecutive impacts has a minor

influence on the outcome of the multi-impact model, which is hereafter assumed to be equally-spaced, unless the interface geometry is explicitly known. Furthermore, Figure 6c depicts the behaviour of $e_{\theta,M}$ of the multi-impact model for blocks that experience inelastic consecutive impacts with $e_N = 0.5$ at the corner of the block (i.e., $\lambda = 1$) interrupted by free-flights [41]. Three different maximum numbers of free-flights and impacts j_{max} are examined, 1, 5 and 25. The results in Figure 6c show convergence for j_{max} values between 5 and 25. This indicates that the model is insensitive to j_{max} for a minimum number of free-flights, which is hereafter assumed to be 5. Finally, Figure 6d compares the proposed multi-impact model with the model of Ther and Kollar [12]. More specifically, the proposed model is equivalent to the model of [12] for any assumed impact position λ_0 and any number of impacts (herein $i_{max} = 5$, which corresponds to 6 impacts) by setting plastic impacts to the proposed model with $e_N = 0$ (intrinsically assumed in [12]).

Section 4.1 revealed that the free-flight analysis does not retain a dimensionless formulation, meaning that the angular CoR in the multi-impact model that includes free-flights is not independent of the angular velocity amplitude, unlike most single-impact models [4, 12, 39, 40]. Therefore, Figure 7 examines the influence of the pre-impact angular velocity amplitude $\dot{\theta}^-$ on the angular CoR $e_{\theta,M}$. $\dot{\theta}^-$ is normalised by $\dot{\theta}_{inst}^- = \sqrt{\frac{3g}{2R}(1 - \cos \alpha)}$, which corresponds to the theoretical maximum pre-impact angular velocity that does not overturn the block under no external excitation [70]. Hence, plausible values of $\dot{\theta}^- / \dot{\theta}_{inst}^-$ typically range between 0 and 1, although occasionally higher values can be reached due to strong external excitations, which may result in overturning. Figure 7 assumes corner impacts (i.e., $\lambda = 1$) and blocks with different sizes R of 1 and 10[m]. In particular, Figure 7a examines blocks with aspect ratio $h/b = 10$ and different values of the

FIGURE 6 | Angular CoR of single-impact $e_{\theta,S}$ (Figure 3) and multi-impact $e_{\theta,M}$ (Figure 4) models for different block aspect ratios: (a) influence of i_{max} on $e_{\theta,M}$ for $\lambda_0 = 0.5$, $e_N = 0$ and equally-spaced λ_i ; (b) influence of equally- and randomly-spaced consecutive λ_i on $e_{\theta,M}$ for $\lambda_0 = 0.5$, $e_N = 0$ and $i_{max} = 5$; (c) influence of j_{max} on $e_{\theta,M}$ for $\lambda = 1$ and $e_N = 0.5$; (d) comparison with the model of Ther and Kollar [12] using $\lambda_0 = 0.5$ and $\lambda_0 = 0.0$, for $e_N = 0$ and $i_{max} = 5$.

FIGURE 7 | Angular CoR of multi-impact model $e_{\theta,M}$ (Figure 4) for different normalised pre-impact angular velocities $\hat{\theta}^- / \hat{\theta}_{inst}$: (a) influence of e_N for $\lambda = 1$ and $h/b = 10$; (b) influence of h/b for $\lambda = 1$ and $e_N = 0.5$.

kinematic normal CoR e_N of 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8, while Figure 7b assumes a kinematic normal CoR $e_N = 0.5$ and investigates three different aspect ratios h/b of 5, 10 and 15. Figure 7 highlights that in all cases the angular CoR of the blocks with different sizes are identical, given the normalisation of the pre-impact angular velocity with $\hat{\theta}_{inst}$. Figure 7a indicates that the velocity amplitude dependency is practically negligible for small values of e_N (e.g., $e_N < 0.5$), while it becomes notable as e_N increases and the pre-impact angular velocity amplitude $\hat{\theta}^-$ increases, resulting in less energy losses at impact. Similarly, Figure 7b reveals trivial dependency on the impact velocity amplitude for slender blocks ($h/b \geq 10$), while a higher dependency is observed for blocks of low aspect ratio and larger values of $\hat{\theta}^-$, resulting in less energy losses at impact. Figure 7 shows that, in all examined cases, the angular CoR remains nearly constant over the plausible range of pre-impact angular velocities $\hat{\theta}^- / \hat{\theta}_{inst} < 1$. This suggests that the explicit dependence on impact velocity can be neglected in practical applications, especially for slender blocks and moderate values of e_N . In view of this observation, for simplicity, the velocity

amplitude dependency is ignored in the parts of the work where only the angular CoR is studied (i.e., Sections 5, 6.2 and 6.3) by evaluating it at a representative intermediate velocity $\hat{\theta}^- / \hat{\theta}_{inst} = 0.5$. In contrast, in Sections 6.4 and 7, where the pre-impact angular velocity is known for each event, it is explicitly accounted for in the computation of the angular CoR.

Furthermore, Section 4.1 proposed the use of a dummy time interval to solve the free-flight phase as a coherent component of the overall multi-impact workflow, implying that the duration of the free-flight is short in comparison with the smooth period of rocking motion, hence overpassing the need for complex numerical integration schemes that alternate states and DoFs rapidly. Figure 8 plots the maximum duration of the free-flight phase (t^{imp}) normalised by the amplitude-dependent period of the free-rocking motion $T = 4p^{-1} \cosh^{-1}((1 - \theta_0/\alpha)^{-1})$ [4]. Similar to Figure 7, Figure 8 considers corner impacts (i.e., $\lambda = 1$) with various kinematic normal CoR e_N values, and blocks with different sizes R and aspect ratios h/b . Overall, Figure 8 illustrates

FIGURE 8 | Maximum free-flight duration t^{imp} normalised by the free-rocking period T of various rotation amplitudes θ_0/α : (c) influence of e_N for $\lambda = 1$ and $h/b = 10$; (d) influence of h/b for $\lambda = 1$ and $e_N = 0.5$.

FIGURE 9 | Angular CoR of impact models for different λ and e_N : (a) single-impact model ($e_{\theta,S}$) for blocks with $h/b = 10$; (b) multi-impact model ($e_{\theta,M}$) for blocks with $h/b = 10$; and (c) ratio of multi- to single-impact models ($e_{\theta,M}/e_{\theta,S}$) for blocks with $h/b = 10$. (d) Limits of the λ and e_N domains for different aspect ratios.

very short time durations of free-flight motion in comparison with the smooth rocking period, lying below 0.5% and occasionally increasing above 1% for stocky blocks and only for rotation amplitudes that correspond to short rocking periods. Therefore, Figure 8 supports the simplification of adopting a dummy period for the free-flight phase.

Figure 9a,b provide an overview of the single- and multi-impact models, respectively, by depicting the resulting angular CoR e_θ (i.e., $e_{\theta,S}$ and $e_{\theta,M}$, respectively) with colour contour for the admissible domains of λ and e_N , specifically for a block with $h/b = 10$ that experiences rocking before impact (i.e., $\theta^- = 0$, $S_x^- = -1$ and $S_y^- = -\text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}^-)$) and for $\mu_s = \mu_d = 0.6$ to prevent sliding. For the multi-impact model, the block is assumed to impact with $\dot{\theta}^- / \dot{\theta}_{inst}^- = 0.5$. Additionally, Figure 9 indicates Equation (18) with a solid line that satisfies equivalence between Housner's and the single-impact model and Equation (19) with a dashed line that corresponds to a zero normal velocity \dot{y}_C^+ at the corner after the single-impact. The single-impact model has a notable inadmis-

sible region due to the penetration constraint of Equation (29) bounded by Equation (19), while the multi-impact model relaxes from this constraint by accounting for consecutive impacts. The equivalence between Housner's and the multi-impact model is also depicted with a line with markers, predicting a value of $e_\theta = 0.985$. More specifically, for the single-impact model $0.97 \leq e_{\theta,S} \leq 1.0$ for $\lambda = 1, e_N = 1$ and $\lambda = 0, e_N = 1$, respectively. On the other hand, the multi-impact model predicts much lower values of $e_{\theta,M}$, i.e., $e_{\theta,M} = 0.85$ for $\lambda = 1$ and $e_N = 1$. Furthermore, the single- and multi-impact models show a very different dependency on the e_N , with the single-impact model exhibiting a minimal gradient along the e_N values in comparison with the multi-impact model, as shown for example by the isoline of equivalence with Housner (line with markers). This indicates a higher sensitivity of the multi-impact model on e_N than the single-impact model.

To facilitate the comparison between the models, Figure 9c shows the ratio $e_{\theta,M}/e_{\theta,S}$ of the multi- and the single-impact models, wherever admissible. This ratio always lies below 1, revealing

that the single-impact model corresponds to an upper-bound limit of the multi-impact model. This stems from the fact that the multiple impacts simulated by the multi-impact model cause higher energy dissipation than the single impact of the single-impact model (also shown in Figure 6). Moreover, the predictions of the single- and multi-impact models coincide with the line indicated by Equation (19), since this corresponds to the condition of the block transitioning to smooth rocking at the end of the first impact. Finally, Figure 9d presents Equations (18), (19) and the equivalence of the multi-impact model with Housner's model for blocks with three different aspect ratios ($h/b = 5$, $h/b = 10$ and $h/b = 15$). Despite the strong influence of h/b on $e_{\theta,M}$, Figure 9d reveals that the main boundaries dictating the λ and e_N domains remain practically unaffected.

6 | Comparison With Experimental Results

This Section provides a validation of the proposed impact models using a thorough comparison with experimental results of free-rocking blocks. The reference experimental campaign [59] is briefly described in Section 6.1, and consists of 120 independent free-rocking tests, spanning over a wide range of aspect ratios. Initially, the two main parameters of the impact model, λ and e_N , are considered as variables and calibrated to better match the experimental observations. To this end, two calibration schemes are followed: (i) Section 6.2 finds the pair of λ and e_N that best fits all the experimental data concurrently, whereas (ii) Section 6.3 sets the values of e_N and calibrates λ uniquely for each test. Finally, Section 6.4 compares a series of representative experimental free-rocking time histories to the response predicted by the impact models.

6.1 | Description of Experimental Campaign

An extensive experimental campaign was conducted to investigate the energy loss of free-rocking blocks [59]. The specimens consisted of 60 limestone blocks with aspect ratios ranging between 4 and 15. More specifically, all the blocks had base width $2b = 0.05[\text{m}]$ and base length $2l = 0.15[\text{m}]$, while there were twelve groups of five blocks each with different heights ranging from $2h = 0.20[\text{m}]$ to $2h = 0.75[\text{m}]$. Each block was tested twice, i.e., once for each base interface, resulting in a total of 120 tests. Before conducting the free-rocking tests, a characterisation campaign was conducted on the limestone blocks and their interface properties [28]. This included measuring a static friction coefficient of $\mu_s = 0.70[-]$, which is incorporated into the following analyses. The characterisation campaign did not estimate the kinematic normal CoR e_N , as its importance was not foreseen before the development of the proposed model. As a result, the comparison of the model with the experimental outcomes is limited to considering the normal coefficient of restitution as unknown, while future experimental studies should encompass the characterisation of this property.

For each free-rocking test, the specimen was placed on top of another limestone block, which was fixed to the base, forming between them a limestone-to-limestone dry contact interface. Then, the free-standing specimen was tilted and laid at a lateral support with an inclination angle higher than its slenderness

angle α . The specimen was gently pushed towards the instability limit until it started the free-rocking motion. The tests were recorded using a contactless digital image correlation system with four cameras surrounding the block and images acquired at a sampling rate of 145 Hz. As a result, the displacement field of each block was reproduced and further post-processed using the Kabsch algorithm to obtain the rigid body motion of the rocking block [59].

The experimental identification of the angular CoR e_θ was conducted with three different methods, using: (i) the angular velocity of the response, denoted $e_{\theta,Vel}$ ("Vel" standing for velocity); (ii) the potential energy of the block at the peaks of the response assuming that energy is lost solely at impacts, denoted $e_{\theta,U}$ ("U" standing for potential energy); and (iii) the potential energy at the peaks of the response and accounting for frictional energy losses at the interface during the rocking phase, denoted $e_{\theta,U+F}$ ("U+F" standing for potential and frictional energies). Further details about the aforementioned methods and the processing of the experimental response can be found in [59]. The first method yielded more scattered results across the different impacts, while the second and third methods showed a steadier response, with minor differences between them since negligible sliding was recorded during the tests. Besides their differences, the experimental datasets of the three methods provided comparable estimations of the e_θ . Figure 10 presents the outcomes of the three different methods for all 120 tests, with a blue circle corresponding to the median value of each test (as the angular CoR was estimated for each distinct impact of every test) and the red colour highlighting the quartile statistics of each aspect ratio h/b , i.e., median, lower and upper quartiles. More specifically, Figure 10a depicts the angular CoR estimated using the first method $e_{\theta,Vel}$, Figure 10b collects the results using the second method $e_{\theta,U}$, and Figure 10c illustrates the outcomes of the third method $e_{\theta,U+F}$. Moreover, Figure 10 shows the prediction of the model of Housner [4], together with the corresponding coefficient of determination R^2 between the experiments and Housner's model. Note that negative values of R^2 indicate that the model fits worse than the average value of the data. Nevertheless, the experimental observations of e_θ lay both above and below the prediction of Housner's model. Hence, other models from the literature that consider Housner's model either as an upper or lower bound could not replicate this variability.

6.2 | Calibration of One Pair of λ and e_N for all Tests

As a first calibration approach of the impact model, it is compelling to find the optimal pair of λ and e_N values that best match the experimental observations e_θ . To this end, all possible combinations of λ and e_N are examined both for the single- and multi-impact models, and their prediction efficiency is calculated in terms of R^2 . Figure 11 plots the computed R^2 for all three different datasets and for both the single- and multi-impact models using a contour map. Additionally, Figure 11 includes the main boundaries of interest of the λ and e_N domain (refer to Section 5 for further details): Equation (18) that satisfy equivalence between the Housner's and the single-impact model, Equation (19) that corresponds to a zero post-impact (normal) velocity at the block's corner after the single-impact, and the

FIGURE 10 | Experimental angular CoR and quartile statistics of each block aspect ratio from 120 free-rocking tests, considering the median value per test and extracted based on: (a) the angular velocity, (b) the potential energy, and (c) the potential and frictional energies.

FIGURE 11 | R^2 between experimental angular CoR and predictions of single- and multi-impact models for different λ and e_N combinations.

associated equivalence between Housner’s and the multi-impact model. Figure 11 illustrates clearly with dense blue colour a narrow band of λ and e_N combinations that provide the higher R^2 , and thus the best match with the experimental observations. The value of R^2 appears to be rather constant along this band, and most importantly, the band coincides closely with the prediction of Housner’s model for all the examined cases. Still, the results indicate that all models perform poorly. For completeness and to facilitate the use of these data, the Appendix provides a simple, data-driven regression of the observed λ – e_N relation together with the associated distribution.

In continuation, Figure 12 collects the best-fitted λ and e_N pairs from Figure 11 and plots the associated predictions of the model of Housner, and the proposed single-impact and multi-impact models against the experimental datasets. For the dataset of $e_{\theta, Vel}$, the proposed models provide a small improvement in the R^2 in comparison with Housner’s model from 18% to 22%, using either $\lambda = 1$ and $e_N = 0.14$ for the single-impact model, or $\lambda = 1$

and $e_N = 0.07$ for the multi-impact model. On the other hand, negligible improvement is observed for the other two datasets ($e_{\theta, U}$ and $e_{\theta, U+F}$), since the best single- and multi-impact models are practically identical to the model of Housner. In summary, Figures 11 and 12 highlight that the proposed model is unable to provide an overall better estimation of the experimental e_{θ} when using one pair of λ and e_N in comparison with the simple-to-use and widely established impact model of Housner. Importantly, this inability of all the models to replicate the experimental e_{θ} stems from the inherent variability of the latter, which, intrinsically, cannot be reproduced by any model with deterministic predictions.

6.3 | Calibration of λ Uniquely per Test for Given e_N

Contrary to Section 6.2, which identifies a single pair of λ and e_N that best fits all the experimental observations, this

FIGURE 12 | Comparison between experimental angular CoR for different aspect ratios with Housner's, single-, and multi-impact models.

Section assumes a constant value of e_N for all the tests, while calibrating λ individually for each test. The physical rationale behind this approach is that the normal CoR e_N can be considered a material-interface property that is universal across all specimens of this experimental campaign, whereas the impact position parameter λ is influenced by the specific irregularities of each contact interface. As a result, each unique interface, and thus each test, may exhibit a distinct and individual value of λ . At the same time, the range of actual values of e_N may be characterised experimentally, even though this was not done in the present experimental characterisation campaign (see Section 6.1).

Figure 13 illustrates the calibration results for all three distinct experimental datasets, comparing both the single- and multi-impact models. Each plot presents the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the fitted parameter λ for varying values of e_N (i.e., $\text{CDF}(\lambda)|_{e_N}$). Dense regions of CDF points with a sharp gradient indicate significance for the calibration process, while sparse regions suggest less relevance for the calibration. These regions allow for an insightful evaluation of how well the models fit the experimental e_{θ} data. Additionally, Figure 13 shows key boundaries in the λ and e_N domain, discussed in Section 5: Equation (18) that represents the equivalence between Housner's and the single-impact model, Equation (19) denotes the condition of zero post-impact (normal) velocity at the block's corner after a single-impact, and the associated equivalence between Housner's and the multi-impact model. Furthermore, the Appendix provides a simple, data-driven regression of the observed λ - e_N relation together with the associated data distribution. The calibration results emphasise that the regions with dense λ CDF points are centred on the Housner equivalence, as also reflected in Figure 11. Nevertheless, the single-impact model is unable to reach significant CDF values, with about half of the tests showing $\lambda = 1$. Conversely, the multi-impact model demonstrates superior calibration across a broader distribution of λ , leading to a more comprehensive interpretation of the experimental observations. Interestingly, the scarce points lying below Equation (19) indicate that this region of the λ and e_N domain (which is inadmissible for

the single-impact model) has limited relevance for interpreting the experimental results.

Moreover, Figure 14 compares the R^2 between the experimental e_{θ} data and the three models: (i) the model of Housner with a continuous black line, (ii) the single-impact model with a dashed orange line, and (iii) the multi-impact model with a dotted red line. The R^2 is constant for the model of Housner, while for the single- and multi-impact models, R^2 is computed for all examined values of e_N using the calibrated CDF distributions of λ shown in Figure 13. Figure 14 demonstrates that both proposed impact models consistently outperform the model of Housner, with the multi-impact model showing superior results compared to the single-impact model. More specifically, the single- and multi-impact models feature the same R^2 for $e_N = 0$. R^2 gradually increases for higher values of e_N . Importantly, the multi-impact model reaches R^2 values exceeding 75%, even for values of $e_N = 0.4$, and it asymptotically approaches 100% at higher values of e_N . These enhanced predictive results occur because the multi-impact model is able to cover and interpret a broader range of lower experimental e_{θ} values (corresponding to the lowest values in Figure 12) as e_N increases, already shown in Figure 9b and reflected by the higher CDF values achieved in Figure 13. Realistic range of values for e_N may be obtained through an experimental characterisation [71]. However, such data was omitted in [28] and remains unspecified in the present study. Nevertheless, Figure 14 indicates that the multi-impact model provides a highly accurate interpretation of the experimental e_{θ} observations by considering reasonable distributions of its input parameters λ and e_N (Figure 13), while neither Housner's nor the single-impact models reach this level of accuracy.

6.4 | Comparison With Experimental Free-Rocking Response Time-History

To assess the reliability of the proposed impact models, Figure 15 compares the experimental free-rocking response time-history of six representative tests with predictions from: (i) the Housner

FIGURE 13 | Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of fitted λ for given value of e_N , calibrated using the experimental angular CoR, for the single- and multi-impact models.

FIGURE 14 | R^2 between experimental angular CoR and predictions of Housner's, single-, and multi-impact models.

model, (ii) the single-impact model, and (iii) the multi-impact model. The responses of these models are generated by solving the equation of motion of the rigid rocking block (Equation (1)), with the only difference being the angular CoR used at impacts. Specifically, the λ and angular CoRs for the single- and multi-impact models are those calibrated in Figure 13, while using $e_N = 0.5$. Moreover, the multi-impact model adopts $i_{\max} = 5$ and $j_{\max} = 5$ (see Figure 6). It is worth noting that the predictions of the different models are not based on calibration of the response in the time-domain, but rely on the extracted angular CoRs from the free-rocking tests (shown in Figure 10) and the calibration process presented in Sections 6.2 and 6.3. The six tests shown in Figure 15 were chosen to cover a wide range of aspect ratios, ranging from $h/b = 4$ to $h/b = 14$, with experimental angular CoR values both above and below Housner's prediction in Figure 10. Firstly, Figure 15 illustrates that Housner's model provides an inaccurate estimate of energy losses, either overestimating (Figure 15a-c) or underestimating (Figure 15d-f), resulting in notable discrepan-

cies with the experimental responses. As an example that reveals the complexity of the problem being addressed, Figure 15c,d illustrates the response of two different blocks with nominally equal geometry ($h/b = 6$), yet the unique interface conditions of the two different blocks being tested make the response dissipate less (Figure 15c) or more (Figure 15d) than Housner's model. In contrast, the proposed single- and multi-impact models demonstrate a marked improvement. In particular, the multi-impact model consistently captures the experimental response across all six tests in Figure 15. The single-impact model also provides accurate predictions for the tests in Figure 15a-c, corresponding to cases where Housner's model under-predicts the angular CoR. However, in the remaining tests, the single-impact model deviates somewhat from the experimental responses, though it still provides a closer match than Housner's model. Overall, Figure 15 highlights the superior performance of the multi-impact model, showcasing its enhanced predictive accuracy relative to both Housner's and single-impact models.

FIGURE 15 | Comparison of the free-rocking response time-history between the experimental results and the results from Housner's, the single- and multi-impact models, for different specimens with various aspect ratios. Both single- and multi-impact models use $e_N = 0.5$, while λ is calibrated using Figure 13.

7 | Influence of the Impact Models on the Dynamic Response of Rigid Rocking Blocks

This Section presents a series of comparative dynamic analyses with the aim of demonstrating the influence of the proposed impact models' parameters on the response of rocking blocks. Both the single- and multi-impact models are examined and compared with Housner's impact model, while three combinations of λ and e_N are investigated, $\lambda = e_N = 0.42$, $\lambda = e_N = 0.7$ and $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$. These values of λ and e_N are chosen to cover the main range of the fitted values in Section 6 (as shown in Figure 13 and Appendix). For the sake of conciseness, they are selected to be equal even though they do not need to. However, this choice conveniently places them on the $x = y$ diagonal in the λ - e_N domain: $\lambda = e_N = 0.42$ is slightly above the inadmissibility limit of Equation (29), $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$ represents an extreme limit case, and $\lambda = e_N = 0.7$ is an intermediate value. The investigation starts with the free-rocking analyses of a representative block, continues with the examination of overturning spectra of a block under anti-symmetric Ricker pulse excitations and finally presents a series of empirical fragility curves using Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) for four different blocks when subjected to 30 recorded ground motions. All analyses consider solely rocking motion using Equation (1) and sliding is disregarded by assuming a sufficiently high friction coefficient.

7.1 | Free Rocking

Figure 16 illustrates the free-rocking response of a block with $h/b = 5$ and $R = 2$ [m], and examines the influence of the adopted impact model and its parameters alongside the impact model of Housner (Equation 3), which remains the same along all the

subplots of Figure 16. More specifically, Figure 16a-c employs the single-impact model and Figure 16d-f uses the multi-impact model, while three combinations of λ and e_N are investigated with $\lambda = e_N = 0.42$ (Figure 16a,d), $\lambda = e_N = 0.7$ (Figure 16b,e) and $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$ (Figure 16c,f). Figure 16 shows that the adopted impact model and its parameters have a significant influence on the free-rocking response, and may result in the motion of the same block with identical initial conditions lasting 50 [s] (e.g., Figure 16a,d) or even less than 3 [s] (e.g., Figure 16f). In general, the higher the values of λ and e_N are, the higher is the energy dissipation at each impact, and thus the faster the motion diminishes. Furthermore, the use of the single- or multi-impact model has appreciable difference only for high values of λ and e_N , while for $\lambda = e_N = 0.42$ the two models are practically identical. As already discussed in Figure 9c, the single-impact model provides an upper bound of the angular CoR of the multi-impact model. Thus the multi-impact model dissipates faster than the single-impact model. Finally, the impact model of Housner presents a unique response that almost coincides with the single-impact model with $\lambda = e_N = 0.7$ (Figure 16b) and occasionally underpredicts (Figure 16a,d) or overpredicts (Figure 16c-f) the response in comparison with the proposed impact models. Overall, Figure 16 underlines the importance of the impact model and energy dissipation in the free-rocking motion of blocks, demonstrating the broad solutions that may be achieved using the proposed models with different parameters.

7.2 | Overturning Spectra Under Anti-Symmetric Ricker Pulses

The response of the rocking block has been extensively studied in the past against pulses since they represent closely near-fault

FIGURE 16 | Comparison of free-rocking response between Housner's and the proposed (a–c) single- and (d–f) multi-impact models, using: (a, d) $\lambda = e_N = 0.42$, (b, e) $\lambda = e_N = 0.7$, and (c, f) $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$. Block details: $h/b = 5$ and $R = 2$ [m].

FIGURE 17 | Overturning spectra of a block with $h/b = 5$ and $R = 2$ [m] using the proposed (a–c) single-impact and (e–g) multi-impact models and (d) Housner's model for: (a, e) $\lambda = e_N = 0.42$, (b, f) $\lambda = e_N = 0.7$, and (c, g) $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$, when subjected to (h) anti-symmetric Ricker pulses.

or pulse-like ground motions [4, 10, 72]. These include sine and cosine functions, or symmetric and anti-symmetric Ricker wavelets, among others [73]. Likewise, this Section examines the overturning spectra of the rocking block of Section 7.1 (with $h/b = 5$ and $R = 2$ [m]) against antisymmetric Ricker wavelet pulses, which are defined as:

$$\ddot{x}_g(t) = \frac{a_g}{1.38} \left(\frac{\omega_g^2 t^2}{3} - 3 \right) \frac{\omega_g t}{\sqrt{3}} e^{-\frac{\omega_g^2 t^2}{6}} \quad (38)$$

where a_g and ω_g are the acceleration amplitude and angular frequency of the Ricker pulse, respectively.

Figure 17 shows the overturning spectra obtained using the single-impact model (Figure 17a–c), the multi-impact model (Figure 17e–g) and Housner's impact model (Figure 17d). The model parameters λ and e_N are $\lambda = e_N = 0.42$ (Figure 17a,e),

$\lambda = e_N = 0.7$ (Figure 17b,f) and $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$ (Figure 17c,g). The horizontal axis refers to the angular frequency of the pulse ω_g (Figure 17h) normalised by the frequency parameter of the block p , and the vertical axis refers to the acceleration amplitude of the pulse a_g (Figure 17h) normalised by the minimum ground acceleration necessary for rocking to initiate $g \tan(\alpha)$. Each spectrum is constructed by a grid of 100×100 points, depicting the results of 10,000 analyses. Figure 17 reports the results of the analyses using colour distinction: orange dots indicate clockwise overturning, red dots represent counter-clockwise overturning, and the blue colour scale indicates safe rocking with colour intensity reflecting the maximum response amplitude $|\theta|_{\max}/\alpha$. From a numerical perspective, overturning occurs when $|\theta| \geq \pi/2$. Moreover, Figure 17h illustrates the Ricker wavelet pulse. Firstly, all spectra in Figure 17 show well-known aspects of block's vulnerability against pulses [10], such as (i) higher excitation amplitudes are required to cause overturning for higher excitation

frequencies, and (ii) there are frequency regions where a certain amplitude results to overturning while a higher amplitude results to safe rocking. Nonetheless, Figure 17 indicates that the different impact models and their parameters (λ and e_N) affect notably the overturning spectra. More specifically, the use of higher values of λ and e_N (see e.g., Figure 17a vs. Figure 17c, or Figure 17e vs. Figure 17g) and the use of the multi-instead of the single-impact model (see e.g., Figure 17a vs. Figure 17e, or Figure 17c vs. Figure 17g) generally result in a shrinkage of the overturning region, since they imply a lower angular CoR and hence higher energy dissipation at impacts. This aspect is more profound for the counter-clockwise overturning region at lower excitation amplitudes (red “bubble” for lower ground motion accelerations). Nevertheless, this general and anticipated observation is not applicable everywhere, since the different angular CoR predicted by the impact models also affect the shape of the overturning boundaries. For instance, the multi-impact model with $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$ in Figure 17g provides a lower angular CoR value than the corresponding single-impact model with $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$ in Figure 17c, yet a pulse with $\omega_g/p = 6.3$ and $a_g/g \tan \alpha = 14.5$ results in overturning for the multi-impact model and safe rocking for the single-impact model. This counter-intuitive outcome stems from the nonlinear nature of rocking motion and underscores the importance of the impact model and its input parameters λ and e_N , ideally characterised experimentally to better reflect the block under consideration.

7.3 | Overturning Fragility Curves Under Recorded Earthquakes

The highly nonlinear behaviour of rocking blocks even under small perturbations and the high record-to-record variability of recorded ground motions limit the generality of the outcomes of the previous deterministic analyses. To this end, this Section extends Sections 7.1 and 7.2, and compares the different impact models through the development of empirical fragility curves using recorded ground motions.

A total of 30 ground motion records are employed to perform IDA on four different blocks. More specifically, the same suite of records employed by previous studies [9] is used herein, composed of ground motions with large magnitude ($M_w = 6.5 - 6.9$) and moderate rupture distances ($R_{rup} < 32.6[\text{km}]$), while further details about the characteristics of the records can be found in [9]. Blocks with four different geometries are considered, with $h/b = 5$ and $h/b = 15$, combined with $R = 1[\text{m}]$ and $R = 3[\text{m}]$. Each block is analysed using Housner’s impact model and both the proposed single- and multi-impact models assuming $\lambda = e_N = 0.42$, $\lambda = e_N = 0.7$ and $\lambda = e_N = 1.0$, resulting in seven different variations. Accordingly, for each case, IDAs are performed for all 30 ground motions and the empirical probability of the response $|\theta|/\alpha$ exceeding a given Limit State (LS) for a given Intensity Measure (IM) $P(|\theta|/\alpha > LS|IM)$ is computed. In particular, two extreme LSs are examined, limited rocking ($|\theta|/\alpha = 0.1$) and overturning ($|\theta| = \pi/2$). The former corresponds to small rotations at operation conditions when rocking is used as a protection strategy, and the latter corresponds to the extreme condition of collapse. The identification of an optimal IM for rocking structures is generally a challenging topic and it is beyond the scope of this work [74, 75]. Herein, two

common dimensionless IMs are considered, i.e., $PGA/g \tan \alpha$ and $pPGV/g \tan \alpha$ (where PGA stands for Peak Ground Acceleration and PGV for Peak Ground Velocity). The former is associated with rocking initiation and the latter is usually better correlated with overturning [76]. Therefore, two fragility curves are constructed for each geometry and impact model: one for the limited rocking LS and $PGA/g \tan \alpha$, and a second for the overturning LS and $pPGV/g \tan \alpha$. More specifically, each IDA is constructed using an IM-basis approach (i.e., vertical statistics) [77] with a constant $PGA/g \tan \alpha$ scaling step of $0.02[-]$, and the analyses are terminated when the first overturning occurs (i.e., possible “resurrections” are neglected [77]). Similar to Section 7.2, overturning is assumed when $|\theta| \geq \pi/2$.

Figure 18 collects the results of 840 IDAs (summing a total of 22,536 dynamic analyses) and depicts two empirical fragility curves: Figures 18a–d using the limited rocking LS for with respect to $PGA/g \tan \alpha$, and Figure 18e–h for the overturning LS with respect to $pPGV/g \tan \alpha$. As expected, Figure 18 shows that stockier (with lower h/b) and larger (with higher R) blocks are more stable in comparison with more slender and smaller blocks (see e.g., Figure 18a,b vs. Figure 18c,d, or Figure 18e,f vs. Figure 18g,h). Furthermore, Figure 18 illustrates that the blocks captured by the impact models with lower λ and e_N , and, hence higher angular CoR, are in more vulnerable for all examined LS-IM combinations. Similarly, when the multi-impact model is compared with the single-impact model, in general, the former yields a more stable response due to its higher energy dissipation. Importantly, these observations are more evident for stockier and smaller blocks (Figure 18a,e) in comparison with more slender and larger blocks (Figure 18d,h). Moreover, Figure 18 illustrates that the influence of the different impact models is comparable for the two examined LSs and IMs, hence corroborating the aforementioned remarks. Overall, Figure 18 allows for a broader overview of the influence of the proposed impact models on the response of blocks under recorded ground motions and highlights the influence of the impact models on the seismic vulnerability of rocking blocks.

8 | Conclusions

This work introduces single-impact and multi-impact models to simulate the planar rocking and rocking-sliding motion of rigid blocks. The single-impact model forms the core of the study, effectively capturing a wide range of impact conditions. It demonstrates notable versatility as it uniquely combines the strengths and features of previously available models, achieving capabilities that none of them individually offered. The model is extended into a multi-impact model, enabling the simulation of consecutive impacts and free-flights. This enhancement increases the model’s efficacy and broadens the scope of its application.

The single-impact model treats the impact event as instantaneous, characterised by a sudden change in angular velocities without any change in displacements or rotations. The position of resultant reaction forces is parametrised by the variable λ , allowing its location to vary along the interface, while the impact can occur at any arbitrary angle θ^- . The impact problem is solved using the linear and angular impulse-momentum equations, coupled with a kinematic normal CoR e_N and a

FIGURE 18 | Fragility curves of rocking blocks with $R = 1$ [m] (top) and $R = 3$ [m] (bottom) and $h/b = 5$, $h/b = 15$ for (a–d) Limit State (LS) $|\theta|/\alpha = 0.1$ and with respect to $PGA/g \tan \alpha$, and (e–h) overturning LS $|\theta| = \pi/2$ with respect to $pPGV/g \tan \alpha$, using Housner’s, single- and multi-impact models and various input parameters λ and e_N .

Mohr-Coulomb friction model with stiction. Post-impact velocities are determined with closed-form, dimensionless formulas, subject to adherence to the necessary physical constraints. The multi-impact model examines the post-impact state of each single-impact and permits the occurrence of multiple consecutive impacts until the block transitions to a smooth rocking motion. These impacts may occur at different points along the contact interface, with the block potentially entering a free-flight phase between instants of impacts.

The performance of the proposed impact models is evaluated through comparisons with experimental results from an extensive campaign comprising 120 free-rocking tests of limestone blocks with a wide range of aspect ratios. The two main parameters of the impact model, λ and e_N , are assumed variables and two calibration schemes are applied to better match the experimental results. The first calibration scheme identifies the optimal pair of λ and e_N that fits all the experimental data simultaneously. Notably, this approach produces estimates comparable to Housner’s model, despite the increased versatility of the proposed models compared to Housner’s simpler formulation. The second calibration scheme assumes a constant e_N , and λ is calibrated individually for each test, significantly enhancing the predictive accuracy of the proposed models. Comparing the two different calibration schemes reveals that models with deterministic predictions are unable to predict the experimental variability of e_θ , while the proposed models that account for the location of impact and surface properties (λ and e_N) allow for a significantly better reproduction of the experimental observations. This improvement is further illustrated through comparisons of free-rocking response time-histories, where the proposed models demonstrate a superior prediction of the experimental response in comparison with Housner’s model. Nevertheless, it is worth emphasising that

the deterministic calibration of a single pair of λ and e_N did not result in a consistent improvement over Housner’s impact model. This suggests that, in practical engineering applications where the impact location and interface properties (λ and e_N) are not known and cannot be calibrated, Housner’s classical impact model remains a robust and convenient default choice. The present study shows that more sophisticated impact models with additional input parameters become particularly valuable within probabilistic frameworks, where uncertainties in the impact conditions can be explicitly represented.

Finally, the study examines the influence of the proposed impact models on the free- and forced-rocking response of rocking blocks using extended comparative analyses. This investigation illustrates that the blocks with impact models that cause higher energy dissipation, in general, result in a more stable response. Importantly, this influence of the impact models on the dynamic response becomes more profound on stockier and smaller blocks, underscoring the importance of the experimental characterisation of the models’ input parameters λ and e_N .

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Appendix: Regression of experimentally calibrated λ and e_N

Sections 5–7 highlight the important influence that the two main parameters of the proposed impact models, λ and e_N , have on the free and

forced rocking response of rocking blocks. Furthermore, the plots of the λ – e_N domain in those sections show a clear correlation between these two parameters, indicating that their values should be chosen carefully. Ideally, λ and e_N require independent experimental characterization, with the former being related to the geometry of the contact interface and the latter being a material-interface property. Nevertheless, such characterisation is commonly lacking in practical applications. To this end, this Appendix offers a regression of the λ – e_N correlation based on the experimentally calibrated data of Section 6. The aim is to provide a data-driven and simple-to-use relation that best describes the calibrated data and their associated uncertainty distribution.

The regression is conducted independently on twelve datasets, associated with: (i) the three different methods to extract the experimental angular CoR (i.e., datasets of $e_{\theta,vel}$, $e_{\theta,U}$ and $e_{\theta,U+F}$, from Section 6.1), (ii) the two calibrations of Sections 6.2 and 6.3 (i.e., calibrating one pair of λ and e_N for all tests, or calibrating uniquely λ for each test for given e_N), and (iii) for both the single- and the multi-impact models. Essentially, the aforementioned twelve datasets are the results of the calibrations shown in Figures 11 and 13. For each case, a simple power law function is fitted, having the form:

$$e_N(\lambda) = C_6(1 - \lambda - C_7)^{C_8} \quad (A1)$$

where C_6 , C_7 and C_8 are the constants of the fitting process. More specifically, Equation (A1) is fitted to the best-performing data (higher R^2) of Figure 11 and the median data points of Figure 13. Consequently, an uncertainty band, defined along the direction perpendicular to Equation (A1), plotted in Figures A1 and A2, later on, is computed from the overall distribution of the data points in the λ – e_N domain. For simplicity, this band is described by a constant standard deviation $\sigma_{68\%}$ (designed to cover 68% of the assumed Gaussian data points), leading to:

$$\lambda_{\pm\text{band}}(\lambda) = \lambda \mp \sigma_{68\%} \frac{m}{\sqrt{1+m^2}} \quad (A2)$$

$$e_{N,\pm\text{band}}(\lambda) = e_N(\lambda) \pm \sigma_{68\%} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+m^2}} \quad (A3)$$

where m is the derivative of Equation (A1) with respect to λ : $m(\lambda) = -C_6 C_8 (1 - \lambda - C_7)^{C_8-1}$. The fitted coefficients of Equation (A1) and the associated standard deviation $\sigma_{68\%}$ are reported in Table A1 and also shown in Figures A1 and A2. Figures A1 and A2 demonstrate that despite the simplicity of the assumed power law, Equation (A1) sufficiently captures the overall trend of the calibrated data points. On the contrary, a constant standard deviation perpendicular to Equation (A1) has some limitations in accurately describing the data along the complete λ – e_N domain, yet it is considered acceptable given its common use in statistics and its interpretable form. Moreover, Table A1 reveals that: (i) the three methods to extract the experimental angular CoR have negligible differences among them, (ii) the one pair of λ and e_N for all data have notably lower standard deviation in comparison with the data where λ was uniquely calibrated for each test (yet the latter showed much better replication of the experimental tests in Section 6.3), and (iii) the main differences between the single- and multi-impact models are the shape coefficients of the regression C_6 , C_7 and C_8 .

In summary, Equations (A1)–(A3) provide a simple, data-driven regression of the experimentally calibrated λ and e_N data of Section 6 and their distribution. Such formulas can be easily used within probabilistic assessment frameworks that consider uncertainties. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that these experimental data are associated with the specific specimens and testing conditions, and caution is advised when extrapolating to other impact conditions, materials, or interfaces.

FIGURE A1 | Counterpart of Figure 11 with the data-fitted regression (Equation A1) and the associated uncertainty bands (Equations A2-A3).

FIGURE A2 | Counterpart of Figure 13 with the data-fitted regression (Equation A1) and the associated uncertainty bands (Equations A2-A3).

TABLE A1 | Regression fitted coefficients and standard deviation.

Dataset	Impact model	Coefficient C_6 [–]	Coefficient C_7 [–]	Coefficient C_8 [–]	Standard deviation $\sigma_{68\%}$ [–]
$e_{\theta, Vel}$, one pair of λ and e_N	Single-impact	3.301	–0.242	2.143	0.087
$e_{\theta, U}$, one pair of λ and e_N	Single-impact	3.948	–0.095	1.885	0.045
$e_{\theta, U+F}$, one pair of λ and e_N	Single-impact	4.044	–0.078	1.870	0.045
$e_{\theta, Vel}$, one pair of λ and e_N	Multi-impact	0.979	–0.110	1.164	0.014
$e_{\theta, U}$, one pair of λ and e_N	Multi-impact	1.043	–0.046	1.166	0.012
$e_{\theta, U+F}$, one pair of λ and e_N	Multi-impact	1.061	–0.030	1.157	0.012
$e_{\theta, Vel}$, unique λ for given e_N	Single-impact	1.925	–0.572	2.809	0.135
$e_{\theta, U}$, unique λ for given e_N	Single-impact	2.343	–0.500	2.386	0.134
$e_{\theta, U+F}$, unique λ for given e_N	Single-impact	2.609	–0.437	2.178	0.134
$e_{\theta, Vel}$, unique λ for given e_N	Multi-impact	0.961	–0.150	1.000	0.134
$e_{\theta, U}$, unique λ for given e_N	Multi-impact	0.956	–0.160	0.982	0.145
$e_{\theta, U+F}$, unique λ for given e_N	Multi-impact	0.952	–0.160	0.992	0.119